

ADVANCE SOCIAL SCIENCE ARCHIVE JOURNAL

Available Online: <https://assajournal.com>
 Vol. 05 No. 01. Jan-March 2026. Page# 2628-2636
 Print ISSN: [3006-2497](#) Online ISSN: [3006-2500](#)
 Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](#)

Marital Disillusionment, Shyness and Psychological Distress in Young Women**Zainab Ali**

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to examine relationship between Marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress. This was hypothesized that marital disillusionment develops shyness and predicts psychological distress in young women. The sample comprises N=145 young married women with obesity. A cross-sectional survey research design was used to execute study of marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress in young women. The scales comprise marital disillusionment questionnaire (Niehuis, S., & Bartell, D 2006) Shyness questionnaire (McCroskey, J. C., & Richmond, V.P., 2013) and k10 psychological distress questionnaire (Hiripi E, Epstein JF, Kessler RC, Barker PR, Colpe LJ, Gfroerer 2003). Demographic information sheets were used as well. To demonstrate marital disillusionment and shyness as the predictors of psychological distress in young women a simple linear regression analysis was conducted. The cross-sectional analysis was undertaken to understand the relationship between marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress. The findings shows that Marital disillusionment is positively correlated with shyness and psychological distress. Shyness is positively correlated with psychological distress. Marital disillusionment predicts shyness and psychological distress in young women. Shyness predicts psychological distress in young women. The result of current study represents an important extension to prior findings and present empirical research provided grounds to more studies in future.

Keywords: Marital Disillusionment, Shyness, Psychological Distress, Scale, Cross-Sectional, Married Women.

Introduction

Marriage is an important event in one's life. It also marks a significant transition in a person's life. The general expectation of both the genders in a marriage is that everything will be good and perfect. However, the situation takes an ugly turn when the expectations are not met. We all are different people with different personalities. Some are lean, some are big in structure while other being obese. How we look or how we appear should not have an impact our marriages. But unfortunately, these factors contribute a lot to success or failure of a marriage. The expectations from a marriage is different for different genders. Both male and female have certain expectations from marriages. As we live in a male dominated society, marriage become even more important for the women. And, to live a happy life, the satisfaction in marriage is very important. However, there are certain factor that led to the marital disillusionment in women with obesity being the one. The marital disillusionment leads to shyness and psychological distress in women which makes the life difficult.

Disillusionment can be described as lapse in positive feelings and perceptions of the spouse about their marriage and rise in negativity, negative feelings and perceptions of the male partner in their marital life. The negative feelings could be as follows but not limited to; ever increasing feelings of disappointment, sense of being defeated, bitterness, less proximity towards partner and hopelessness in the marriage. In

the following sections, we will outline the, The Disillusionment in Marriage Theory traces its origins to the idealization of a couple's connection and one another during the courtship phase, supporting and demonstrating the predictive value of disillusionment for later marital instability. We'll wrap up with describing the marital disillusionment scale, which is used to gauge how disillusioned a couple is.

According to Oflaz, A. (2019), shyness is defined as an obsession with one's thoughts and behaviors that causes discomfort in social circumstances. It may range from little displeasure and strange sentiments when the others are present or in social settings, resulting in traumatic periods of anxiety that harms an individual's life C. J.W.H. (2019). Shyness is mostly about apprehending about the negative perceptions of an individual being evaluated in social circles, according to C. J.W.H. (2019).

It involves uncomfortable, tense, unpleasant, and uneasy feelings when with strangers or regular acquaintances according to (Kaur et al., 2023). the shy people may stay reserved while in public, however, they are continuously suffering from inside and in a state of turmoil. They predominantly focus on their inner thoughts and reactions and how the out-world deal with them. Crozier opines that the Shy children experience social fear and anxiety in new social settings and feeling of embarrassment and self-conscious when they perceive themselves as being socially evaluated or the centre of attention.

Shyness involves an approach-avoidance conflict. According to (Liang et al., 2023) Though social dread and anxiety induce a competing avoidance motivation, which concurrently inhibits the shy children's desire and incentive for social involvement, both are present in shy youngsters. A primary concern for a shy a person is interpersonal interactions. However, some types of interactions also result in increased level of shyness in individuals. According to research, five situations are associated with shyness. The first among them is The Interaction with authoritative Personalities, second is when a shy person encounters a person from the opposite sex, third one is when they interact with strangers, fourthly, when they are among members of small group and they are the focus of attention and finally, when they are in evaluative situations e.g. let us say, job interviews etc.

Psychological distress has been conceptualized by Gulbahce, O., and Gulbahce, A et al., (2019) as devoid of enthusiasm, insomnia (inability to fall or stay asleep), depression or blues, hopelessness about the future, emotional distress (prone to cry), monotony or a fleeting concern in things, and the thoughts of suicides. (Morgan et al., 2023) is of the opinion that psychological distress is the unpleasant subjective state of anxiety and sorrow that manifests emotionally and physiologically as tenseness, restlessness, worry, irritability, and fear. They went on to say that psychological distress can range widely in intensity, from moderate to severe, with the latter being linked with mental problems such schizoaffective disorder. In a different study, Chalfant et al. Defined psychological distress as a recurring condition of melancholy, anxiety, impatience, and challenging interpersonal relationships. Due to extreme stress, we face unpleasant feelings. This state of unpleasant feelings and restlessness is known as psychological stress and problem. This situation disturbs our ordinary activities and our mode of inter action with other fellow beings.

Psychological discomfort has long been controversially understood. The term's definition and what constitutes an assertion that a person is suffering psychological distress have been the primary points of disagreement among academics who have studied psychological distress (Viertiö, S., et, al., 2021).

Rationale

The aim of this study was to analyse the relationship between marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress. As marital disillusionment has stronger associations with shyness and psychological distress so did, we assess the relationship between these variables. Our purpose is to analyse do marital disillusionment have any connection with young women. we have found that marital disillusionment is positively correlated with shyness and psychological distress. There are so many articles, journals and studies on marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress. This research on marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress only includes young women. Our research found out that these variables are interlinked with each other as marital disillusionment shyness and psychological distress are positively correlated with each other. Another reason to study these constructs was to find out if the young women have more issues of disillusionment in their marriages or not. Furthermore, this study will add to the existing body of literature in Pakistan.

Objectives

1. To identify the relationship between marital disillusionment and psychological distress in women.
2. To identify if marital disillusionment is responsible for the development of shyness in young women.
3. Marital disillusionment predicts psychological distress in young women.

Hypotheses

1. Marital disillusionment will be positively correlated with psychological distress in young women.
2. Marital disillusionment will be positively correlated with shyness in young married women.
3. Shyness will be positively correlated with psychological distress in young married women.

Methodology

This section included topics i.e. research Design, Sampling approach, Inclusion criteria, segregation Criteria, Sample characteristic, Operational definitions, Assessment measures, Producer and Ethical deliberation for data collection.

Research Design

A cross-sectional research design was used in the present study to assess the relationship of Marital disillusionment, shyness and psychological distress.

Sample and Sample Strategy

The sample was calculated through G power calculator. Sample was recruited using purposive sampling for data collection according to following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria

- Young women were included.
- Married women we're included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Male partners of the female Participants were not Included in this research.
- Mentally impaired women were excluded.

Assessment Measures

Following assessment measures are used in the present study.

1. Demographic sheet
2. Marital disillusionment Scale.
3. Shyness Scale
4. Psychological distress Scale

Demographic information Sheet

Demographic information sheet is used to gather personal information. It included Name, Age, Gender (male, female) Family income (fifty thousand, fifty thousand to one lac, more than one lac) occupation, family system (joint, nuclear), Family background (Rural, Urban) Working status, BMI index, obesity as a source of disillusionment.

Table 3.1

Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=100)

Demographics	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>F</i>	%
Age of the participant	23.33	1.65		
No of Siblings	2.82	1.44		
Weight	77.14	6.34		
Birth order	2.99	1.31		
Occupation				
Not working			95	79.2
Working			25	20.8
Monthly Income				
50000			33	27.5
50,000 Plus			49	40.8
1 Lac			38	31.7
Family System				

Joint			76	63.3
Nuclear			44	36.7
Marital Status				
Married			120	100.0
UnMarried			0	0
Nature of Meriage				
Love			44	36.7
Arrange			76	63.3
Years Of Obesity				
5 years			41	34.2
10 years			29	24.2
More than 10			50	41.7
Other Member with Obesity				
NO			45	37.5
Yes			75	62.5
Obesity As A Source Of Disillusionment				
Yes			26	21.7
No			56	46.7
May Be			38	31.7

Assessment Measures

Marital disillusionment scale (Niehuis, S., & Bartell, D 2013)

The Marital Disillusionment Scale. Measurement Instrument Database for the Social Science. Scale for Marital Disillusionment has 16 items.

Shyness Scale (McCroskey, J. C., & Richmond, V.P., 2013)

Scale for shyness has 14 items. That scale has a response format like; 1. (*strongly Disagree*) 2. (*Disagree*) 3. (*Neutral*) 4. (*Agree*) and 5. (*strongly Agree*).

Psychological distress Scale (Hiripi E, Epstein JF, Kessler RC, Barker PR, Colpe LJ, Gfroerer 2003)

Psychological Distress Scale developed by Kessler (K10). Ten items concerning emotional states are included in the K10 scale, each having a five-level response range.

The results of the present research are designed to explore the relationship between marital disillusionment, shyness and psychological distress in young women. The data analytic strategy starts with reliability analysis using Cronbach’s alphas for scales. Further, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to assess the relationships between marital disillusionment, shyness and psychological distress in young women with obesity. Multiple hierarchical regression was run to assess the mediating role of shyness between marital disillusionment, and psychological distress in young women with obesity.

Reliability Analysis

The data mentioned below is reliability and descriptive analyses for each measure used for assessment; the ranges are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1

Descriptive analyses for each assessment measure (N = 120)

Variable	M	SD	Range	Chronbeck α	Skewness	Kurtosis
Marital Disillusionment	85.38	16.22	19 – 112	.95	-1.67	1.67
Shyness	49.91	12.50	16 – 67	.89	-.87	-.22
Psychological Distress	34.78	7.45	11 – 48	.86	-1.19	1.43

Note. M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The above table showed the means and standard deviations, number of items, reliabilities and maximum and minimum ranges of assessment measures Alpha reliability of study variables and skewness and kurtosis as a measure of normality of data. The analysis revealed a satisfactory range of reliability for marital disillusionment, shyness and psychological distress indicating high reliability moreover, the value

of skewness and kurtosis was within the acceptable range +2 and -2 (Hier et al., 2023) indicating normal distribution.

As reliability provided an initial baseline, furthermore Pearson product moment correlation analysis was carried out to assess the relationship between study variables.

Main Analyses

Pearson product-moment correlation analysis was applied to examine the association between study variables marital disillusionment, shyness and psychological distress. It was provisionally reported that there would be a correlation between the variables. Demographics were also included in the results to check if there is any link between the demographics and the research variables.

Table 4.2
Correlational analysis between the study variables (N = 150)

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Age	23.33	1.64	-	.18*	-	.10	-	-	.15	-.06	.05	.18*	.03	-.04	.16	-.07	-.01
No of Siblings	2.81	1.43	-	-	-.07	-.05	-.22*	-.08	.15	-.06	.07	.18*	.03	-.04	.16	.07	.10
Weight	77.14	6.34			-	.10	.06	.11	-.06	.05	-.12	-.08	.06	.04	.01	-.06	.03
Birth order	2.99	1.30				-	-.28*	-.03	.07	.12	.00	-.05	.18*	-.02	.05	.01	-.00
Education	1.84	.71					-.34**	-.08	-.29**	.12	-.11	-.10	.03	-.01	-.12	.10	
Occupation	.20	.40						-.37**	-.20*	.13	.00	.14	-.09	.01	-.00	.04	
Monthly Income	2.04	.77							-.46**	-.04	.14	.02	.06	-.01	.05	-.10	
Family System	1.36	.48								.04	-.12	.19*	-.15	-.02	.01	.10	
Nature of marriage	1.63	.48									.16	.08	.03	.04	-.07	-.03	
Years Of Obesity	2.07	.87										.22*	-.06	-.04	-.10	-.22*	
Other Member with Obesity	.62	.48											-.05	.01	.11	-.00	
Obesity As a Source of Disillusionment	2.10	.72												.08	-.06	.08	
Marital Disillusionment	85.38	16.21													.31*	.67**	

Weight	-0.01	-.22	.20	.11	-.00		
Birth order	.12	-1.04	1.29	.59	.02		
Education	1.57	-2.42	5.56	2.01	.15		
Occupation	.41	-3.26	4.09	1.85	.02		
Monthly Income	.41	-3.26	4.10	1.859	.04		
Family System	1.26	-2.09	4.62	1.69	.08		
Nature of marriage	-.37	-3.36	2.60	1.50	-.02		
Years Of Obesity	-2.12	-3.80	-.44	.84	-.24*		
Other Member with Obesity	1.09	-2.00	4.19	1.56	.07		
Obesity as a Source of Disillusionment	.99	-.91	2.91	.96	.09		
Step II						.52***	.41***
(Constant)	3.47	-21.27	28.22	12.48			
Age	.08	-.58	.75	.33	.02		
No of Siblings	.31	-.44	1.06	.37	.06		
Weight	-.01	-.17	.14	.08	-.01		
Birth order	-.16	-1.02	.70	.43	-.02		
Education	1.74	-1.19	4.69	1.48	.16		
Occupation	.23	-2.47	2.95	1.36	.01		
Monthly Income	1.15	-1.57	3.87	1.37	.11		
Family System	1.75	-.72	4.23	1.25	.11		
Nature of marriage	-1.07	-3.27	1.13	1.11	-.07		
Years Of Obesity	-1.61	-2.85	-.37	.62	-.18*		
Other Member with Obesity	.38	-1.90	2.67	1.15	.02		
Obesity as a Source of Disillusionment	.28	-1.13	1.70	.71	.02		
Marital Disillusionment	.30	.24	.37	.03	.66***		
Step III						.58***	.06***
(Constant)	-6.84	-30.73	17.04	12.04			
Age	.12	-.50	.75	.31	.02		
No of Siblings	.31	-.39	1.01	.35	.06		
Weight	.01	-.14	.16	.07	.01		
Birth order	-.05	-.86	.76	.41	-.00		
Education	2.26	-.51	5.05	1.40	.21		
Occupation	.12	-2.43	2.67	1.28	.00		
Monthly Income	1.33	-1.23	3.89	1.29	.13		
Family System	1.73	-.59	4.07	1.17	.11		
Nature of marriage	-.82	-2.90	1.25	1.04	-.05		
Years Of Obesity	-1.28	-2.46	-.10	.59	-.15*		
Other Member with Obesity	-.18	-2.36	1.98	1.09	-.01		
Obesity as a Source of Disillusionment	.47	-.86	1.81	.67	.04		
Marital Disillusionment	.27	.20	.33	.03	.58***		
Shyness	.15	.07	.23	.04	.26***		

Multiple hierarchal regression was run to assess the mediating role of shyness between marital disillusionment and psychological distress in women. Results indicated that there was independent of observations Durban Watson value was between 1 – 3. Results also indicated that in step 1, the model explain 11% variance. Model 2 explained 41% variance, results indicated that women who experienced obesity for longer period of time had more psychological distress.

Results of step two show that model explain 41% variance. Results suggested that marital disillusionment was a significant positive predictor of psychological distress. Step 3 indicated that model explain 6% variance. Results reported that it was a significant positive predictor of psychological distress. Overall results indicated shyness was partially mediated between marital disillusionment and psychological distress.

Summary of findings

- Marital disillusionment was the only and strongest positive predictor of shyness
- Results indicated that women who experienced obesity for longer period of time had more psychological distress.
- Marital disillusionment was a significant positive predictor of psychological distress.
- Shyness was a significant positive predictor of psychological distress.
- Shyness was partially mediated between marital disillusionment and psychological distress.

Conclusion

The present research designed to explore the relationship between marital disillusionment, shyness, and psychological distress in young women. Pearson product-moment correlation analysis was applied to examine the association between study variables marital disillusionment, shyness, and psychological distress. Result indicated that marital disillusionment was positively correlated with shyness. Shyness was positively correlated with psychological distress. And marital disillusionment was positively correlated with psychological distress. Among demographics, only years of having obesity was negatively correlated with psychological distress. Furthermore, regression analysis showed that marital disillusionment positively predicted shyness. Shyness positively predicted psychological distress. And marital disillusionment positively predicted psychological distress. Among demographics, only years of having obesity negatively predicted psychological distress. Moreover, shyness partially mediated the relationship between marital disillusionment and psychological distress.

Limitations and Suggestions

The following are the limitations and suggestions of this research.

1. The present study had many methodological limitations as well as there are some suggestions also. Tools used in this research were constructed according to the West culture. Local tools need to be developed.
2. Scales need to be developed on the basis of our indigenous standards. Scale construction is beyond our scope due to lack of resources in the terms of money, time, and expertise of the researchers.
3. Generalization of the finding could be limited due to the fact that this article was correlational in nature. Longitudinal research article can likely help in disclosing better support on this article.
4. Ecological and some scenario-specific elements were not taken into account and were not investigated in this study.
5. Qualitative research can be done for in-depth understanding.
6. It is proposed that more comprehensive research needs to be carried out in order to reveal the variables which impact marital disillusionment, shyness, and psychological distress in women. Additional articles must be written on bigger and more reflective samples by applying longitudinal research articles, so results of the research articles could be generalized broadly.

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